

Study On Promotion Mix Strategy Towards Big Bazaar Bidar

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Abstract- Managing human resources in today's dynamic environment is becoming more and more complex as well as important. Recognition of the people as a valuable resource in the organization has led to increase in the trends of employee maintenance, job security, etc The research project deals with the, "promotion mix strategy" as carried out at Big bazaar Ltd Bidar. The project involves performance appraisal, skill assessment and skill development process. This project study deals with detailed company and industry profile including company's history. Its activities, operations, organization structure etc. This project attempts to give detailed information about the company and the nature of its functioning along with the detailed theoretical information about various skill sets necessary among the employees for the overall functioning of the individual.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thanks to the project coordinator and my internal guide and external guide to the wonderful opportunity to improve my practical knowledge and understanding the you ought to send a see of one (or an extra) much obliged. Which you could send one to your boss straight, to your product boss or temporary position organizer, and to an additional buddy who can help you out or get worried for your regular work for the time of your instructing. Send a thank-you word empowering you to explicit your gratitude for the opportunity. In addition, these respectful contacts bolster you finish the temporary job on an idealistic and incredible notification.

That is a representation of a thanks word which you can send (by method of email or mail) in the wake of finishing your temporary position. For example this thanks word can be utilized to affirm "thank you" on your temporary position ability or for calling proposal.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE RESEARCH

The period of time 'limited time join' is utilized to be able to counsel the combination of sort of specific instruments that are being used by the firm to sell its product and commercials situated.

• Promotion Mix Strategy

The essential special instruments or exercises that make up a blend of advancements are private income, advancing, exposure and deals advancing. That is frequently alluded to as a detail of limited time blend.

Philip Kotler says, "The organization's finished publicizing and showcasing interchanges consolidate is also assembled a blend of advancements with a blend of promoting, individual deals, deals advancement, open individuals from the family and direct advertising instruments utilized for organizations to seek after advancing and publicizing purposes. "

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study was conducted to know the problems faced by the employees and also there perception regarding their future growth prospects and other benefits given by the company researcher should identify whether the employees are expecting improvement and upgraded facilities

3.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the awareness level of big bazaar in bidar city
- To understand the promotion mix of different companies in big bazaar.
- To study the factors influencing promotion mix strategy of different companies at big bazaar.

- To understand the customers perception towards promotion mix strategy of different companyat big bazaar.
- To understand different promotion mix strategy adopted by different companies in promotion mix strategy big bazaar
- To understand the concept of promotion mix strategy of big bazaar bidar.
- Methods of sales Promotions mix activity in big bazaar

3.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- This study is focuses on understand the knowledge of bidar in deep level.
- Bidar people have a many choices in choosing particular brands in big bazaar bidar.
- It make more difficult to the organisation. The big bazaar has makes differentiate to its products, from other competitors.
- This study would give the basic understanding and the dynamics of marketing of
- Big bazaar owns branded products and other products.
- It would also be a frame work for any further studies in the field of marketing of big bazaar .
- Data is gathering in relation to the dealers opinion on various branded items of big bazaar and future group products.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

GRAPH 4.1: shows since how long customers have been shopping in big bazaar.

GRAPH 4.2: shows promotional activity of big bazaar motivates to buy.

GRAPH 4.3: Shows if yes

On which factor (promotional activity) motivates to buy.

GRAPH 4.4: shows being loyal customers of big bazaar are you expecting more offers and discounts from big bazaar

GRAPH 4.5: shows is current promotion (offers) activity enough (sufficient) for future big bazaar customers

GRAPH 4.6: Shows which promotion activity is big bazaar has to concentrate or improve.

GRAPH 4.7: shows is personal selling of big bazaar promotional activity helps to choose the products

GRAPH 4.8: shows do you think is big bazaar providing various products on regional or good prices

GRAPH 4.9: Shows which category customer prefer to buy more products in big bazaar.

GRAPH 4.10: Suggestion to improve our services

CONCLUSION

Here i observed that the big bazaar is providing a high tuff competition to other retail store. And through its strong performance big bazaar created its own brand in the market .the big bazaar offers and its best prices are pocket friendly to the customers. Big bazaar need to know the pulse of non metro city people like Bidar, and other undeveloped cities.

Big bazaar need to build a strong relation with the bidar people somewhere it failed to reach bidar people. Because the Big bazaar not that much created awareness about its products and services, And benefits to the people.

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